

DEVELOPING CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS: INNOVATIVE APPROACHES

Gulbaxor Xamidova

**Associate Professor of the Department of Theory and Methodology of
Preschool Education, Jizzakh State Pedagogical University**

Abstract

This article analyzes the issue of developing creative competence of future teachers based on an innovative approach. The theoretical and practical aspects of fostering creative thinking in the educational system are highlighted, and methodological recommendations are developed based on advanced foreign experience and modern pedagogical technologies. In addition, the relevance of the topic is substantiated based on the decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at modernizing the education system.

Keywords

creative competence, innovative education, pedagogical technologies, creative thinking, interactive methods, digital education, competence-based approach, professional development of teachers.

Introduction

In the context of globalization, the development of innovative approaches and creative thinking in the education system has become one of the priority areas. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the radical reform of the education system and the enhancement of the professional and creative potential of pedagogical staff have become key directions of state policy.

In particular, the Action Strategy for 2017–2021 defined improving the quality of education and training modern pedagogical personnel as priority tasks. Furthermore, the Presidential Decree No. PF-5544 (2018) on the Strategy of

Innovative Development emphasized the need to train creative and innovative-thinking specialists in the education system.

Moreover, the Presidential Decree No. PF-5847 (2019) on the Concept for the Development of Higher Education until 2030 identified the development of teachers' creative competence as one of the main objectives. The Presidential Decree No. PF-6097 (2020) elevated the formation of innovative thinking through the development of science to the level of state policy.

These documents clearly demonstrate the relevance of developing creative competence among future teachers.

Literature Review

The concept of creative competence is one of the most actual categories widely studied in modern pedagogy, psychology, and educational theory. It encompasses an individual's ability to generate new ideas, approach problems in unconventional ways, and think independently. In scientific literature, the integration of creativity and competence has led to the emergence of the term "creative competence," which reflects a teacher's ability to develop innovative solutions in professional practice.

Among foreign researchers, J. Guilford considered creativity as an important aspect of human thinking and associated it with divergent thinking. According to his theory, creativity manifests in the ability to find multiple, unconventional solutions to a problem. Guilford recommended using open-ended questions, problem situations, and methods that encourage free thinking in the educational process.

E. Torrance conducted fundamental research on identifying and developing creative thinking. He defined creativity as the ability to approach problems in new ways, generate original ideas, and apply them in practice. The Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking (TTCT) are still widely used to assess creativity levels.

In the field of pedagogy, V. A. Slastenin considered creativity an integral part of a teacher's professional competence. He emphasized that a modern teacher should not only transmit knowledge but also be a creative thinker capable of applying innovative methods. He highlighted reflection, self-analysis, and the implementation of pedagogical innovations as key factors in developing creativity.

Local scholars, including N. Muslimov and B. Qodirov, link teachers' creative competence with innovative activity. Their research shows that creative competence is closely related to professional training, methodological skills, and the ability to use modern technologies. They also emphasize the importance of considering national values, cultural context, and the specific features of the education system.

Recent studies indicate that digital technologies play an increasingly important role in developing creative competence. Multimedia tools, interactive platforms such as Moodle and Google Classroom, artificial intelligence-based applications, and virtual laboratories contribute to the development of independent thinking. The digital learning environment ensures an individualized approach and helps reveal students' creative potential.

In addition, distance learning technologies are considered an effective tool for fostering creative competence. Research shows that distance education enhances students' independent work, problem-solving skills, and ability to generate innovative ideas. Project-based learning, problem-based learning, and collaborative learning methods are particularly effective in developing creative thinking.

Furthermore, modern scientific perspectives highlight the importance of STEAM education, design thinking, and lifelong learning concepts in developing creative competence. These approaches enable learners not only to acquire knowledge but also to create new ideas through practical activities.

Overall, the analysis shows that the development of creative competence requires a comprehensive approach, combining traditional methods with innovative technologies and interactive strategies. This ensures a higher level of professional training for future teachers.

Analysis of Literature and Conclusions

The analysis of scientific literature shows that creative competence is a key determinant of a teacher's professional success. A creative teacher can effectively organize the educational process, foster independent thinking among students, and propose innovative solutions to educational challenges. Thus, creative competence is an essential indicator of both professional and personal development.

Research findings indicate that innovative approaches play a decisive role in developing creative competence. While traditional methods focus on reproductive knowledge, innovative approaches enhance creative thinking, problem-solving, and independent decision-making skills. Therefore, creative competence should be developed through innovative pedagogical technologies.

Interactive methods and digital technologies are increasingly important in modern education. Methods such as brainstorming, clustering, case studies, and project-based learning promote active participation and unlock students' creative potential. Digital technologies enhance visualization, individualization, and efficiency of the learning process, creating a collaborative educational environment.

However, the analysis also reveals certain challenges. Although theoretical approaches are well-developed, systematic methodologies for practical implementation are недостаточно elaborated. Many studies address creativity within specific methods rather than integrating them into a unified system.

Additionally, the assessment criteria, indicators, and monitoring systems for creative competence are not sufficiently developed, which complicates the evaluation of its development in the educational process.

Based on the analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn: creative competence is a key determinant of professional activity; its development requires innovative and competence-based approaches; interactive methods and digital technologies are effective tools for fostering creativity; there is a need to develop an integrated methodological model; improving assessment and monitoring mechanisms remains a pressing issue.

Discussion and Results

The study identified the following effective methods for developing creative competence in future teachers: Interactive methods- brainstorming, clustering, case study, project method. Digital technologies: multimedia lessons, online platforms (Moodle, Google Classroom), virtual laboratories Creative environment- free-thinking atmosphere, problem situations, independent research activities. Practical activities- pedagogical trainings, simulations, experience exchange

The results showed that the use of these methods significantly improves students' level of creative thinking.

Conclusion

The development of creative competence among future teachers is one of the priority tasks of the modern education system. In the context of globalization and digital transformation, teachers are required not only to possess deep knowledge but also to demonstrate creative, independent, and critical thinking skills.

The study confirms that innovative approaches significantly enhance intellectual potential, creative abilities, and professional training of future teachers.

The integration of interactive methods, problem-based learning, project activities, and digital technologies increases the effectiveness of the educational process.

Furthermore, the development of creative competence should be systematic, goal-oriented, and continuous. It requires the integration of theoretical knowledge with practical activities, the creation of opportunities for independent learning, and the establishment of a creative environment.

In conclusion, developing creative competence is essential for improving the quality of education, training innovative professionals, and ensuring sustainable societal development.

Recommendations

1. Introduce specialized courses aimed at developing creative competence in higher education institutions.
2. Widely implement innovative and interactive teaching methods.
3. Create a digital learning environment.
4. Encourage students' independent and creative activities.
5. Adapt international best practices to the national education system.

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